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Abstract: this article describes the concept and structure of the food supply system. Although the concepts of food supply and food security are used in the same sense. From the history of the origin of food supply to the current issues of food supply, it is covered.

Key words: food supply, category, food security, food independence, population food consumption, production, resources.

Currently, due to the decrease in the level of food supply in the countries of the world, the issue of food security has become more acute than ever, although a certain part of the country's politicians and scientists reject it and consider it unacceptable. -market, without economic content and too politicized.

At the same time, the problem of food security entered the agenda of world politics in the early 70s, when one of the UN organizations (FAO) developed its international strategy, and it became a topic of constant discussion at the intergovernmental level.

"Food security" is an officially accepted term in world practice, used to describe the state of the food market in an entire country or an integrated group of countries. It is provided with appropriate resources and capacity, regardless of external and internal conditions and threats, the state guarantees the ability to satisfy the population's need for food products in sufficient quantity, quality and assortment for their healthy physical and social development, and determines. Food safety. Also, all strata of the population are characterized by the level of effective demand that is sufficient to purchase certain food products.

FAO experts define international food security as the provision of guaranteed access to food products in the amount necessary for an active healthy life for all people at all times. One of the most important indicators of the state of food security of countries, as well as of the whole world (according to FAO categories), is the "dynamics of grain production per capita". The overall lower limit of food security for the country is 600 kg of production per capita per year.

Food security is the most important component of national security, and it describes not only the economic, but also the political independence of the existing system, the ability to meet the needs of citizens without compromising the security of the national state.

A country's ability to maintain food security as a result of a country's total or partial reliance on external food supplies determines its food independence.

The World Food Conference (Rome, 1996) decided on the principles of state responsibility for food security at the level of the individual, the region, the country and the whole world community. In recent years, effective national food security strategies have been developed and used in countries such as Japan, South Korea, and the European Union.

The problem of food security was a part of economic studies and domestic science. Many works consider the country's participation in international trade in food and protective measures [7, 14, 15, 18, 66, 61, 121, 128] - an important number associated with the growth of the food

economy of the world's regions. global food crisis [8,66,101, 66 181, 139]: in developed countries - shortages associated with increased food production. The state of rural ecology attracts the country's scientific community in the context of mass access to modern technologies.

When scientists define the concept of food security, it is measured by the level and conditions of the country's agricultural products and the provision of conditions, taking into account self-management for the country, its development includes protecting manufacturers in the range of 80-85% and critical - in the range of 75%.

The analysis of the situation shows that it is necessary to formulate the principles of the current and future conditions for the development of the Russian food sector, because it is the basis for ensuring the well-being of the population. the objective for support should take into account the specific characteristics of the country arising from natural conditions.

The main provisions of the state strategy of the country's economic security, approved in April 1996, for this purpose, write down the system of the most important national interests, including: the possibilities of the country's national economy as far as possible independent of external influence; increase and maintain the standard of living of the population, which determines the socio-economic stability of the population; Maintaining a single economic space; Regulation of economic processes by the state. Food standards of national production are determined by a special agreement in 1995, including the volume and dynamics of imported goods and dynamics, including the share of turnover of the national market. employment dynamics with

A necessary condition for the food security of our country is "food independence", which includes meeting the main part of food needs due to local production.

Food independence is the ability to ensure the necessary level of the country's economy in case of complete or partial suspension of external food products. Food independence is ensured even if the share of food imports does not exceed 16% in the total volume of their consumption (according to FAO recommendations). The idea of self-management of food products, the growth of the production of the Domestic Agro-Sanifical complex, the development of many other sectors of the economy, the development of other areas of food are fighting against the crisis of the international market and other external threats.

The transition from the planning and distribution system to the market and the state's management of the economy, the food support of the country's population was provided by market elements and the power of food expansion. The loss of economic security in the total consumption of imported products creates a dependence on the global food market, which increases the instability of the domestic market. A sharp decrease in food imports in August 1998, which creates conditions for political and economic pressure on the country's exporters, is against their national interests. Therefore, there is an urgent need to formulate fundamentally different state policies in the field of food support, the need to justify the target attitude, strategic and tactical directions and tactics.

Quantitative assessment of the level or state of food security of the country can be done using the dynamics of two groups of indicators:

- the level of consumption of basic food products, taking into account their differences in groups of the population with different incomes;
- the degree of self-government of the country with food.

In both groups, real and deficient indicators are distinguished, i.e. Minimum (maximum) allowed. In the first group of indicators, medical standards can be previously used scientifically

based social standards. Current and forecast indicators of the financial and economic status of producers, including food imports, are used.

In January 1996, the State Duma of the country adopted a decision "On measures for the food security of the country and the supply of food products to the population." Based on it, the law "On Food Safety of the Country" has not yet been signed by the President of the country and has been reviewed by the State Duma. As part of the system of legislation on national security issues, the law regulates the state policy on the supply of food products to the population, as well as legal relations in the field of production, storage, processing and distribution of products. Protect the company in general and every a citizen separates threats and negative factors from threats and negative factors related to lack of consumption or low-quality food. The main purpose of the law is to guarantee the population's right to full nutrition as one of the conditions for the realization of human rights, for the realization of the rights to life, other non-citizen rights.

Due to the development of the above laws and doctrines on food safety, many researchers reduce the problem of food safety to the problems of food safety, but the food supply system includes a wide range of them.

The security of the food supply system or food safety defines the limiting parameters of the system, the violation of which creates threats to the security of the country. In other words, safety is one of the conditions or one aspect of the food supply system. This is the difference between the concepts of food safety and food security.

As for the term food supply, it has long been widely used in economic literature, but the food supply system has not been singled out as an independent research topic. As a rule, food problems were taken into account in the context of the general problem of agricultural development or the general problem of organizing the supply of food products to the food market.

Under the conditions of an open economy, the justification of the meaning of the food aspect in the country's economy and the development of the agro-industrial complex should be based on the political, socio-ecological goals of development and the skills of state priorities. The main importance of the state is the goals of the political tone, among which the leading place is occupied by food security, which is the provision of access to food in an unlimited amount of time for the state and society, and sufficient and extraordinary for the healthy and social development of everyone in personal conditions. the minimum necessary to maintain health and working capacity under the circumstances. It follows that in the development of agricultural policy, the state has a sufficient degree of ownership of the power of the population, at least in terms of stopping the population's energy imports. The need to ensure a certain level of production is determined by two main reasons. First, if the level of own production is not enough to electrify the government for the minimum standards, then there are negotiations on large-scale political and economic issues of the state, additional possibilities of pressure have been created in the country. complete suspension of food imports (trade embargo) to temporarily deny humanitarian aid in case of famine and other natural disasters. Secondly, the food market and most of the imports directed to the world market are the stability of the domestic market, therefore the whole economy is more volatile than the world markets in developed countries and there are almost no regulators. The second level is the goals of a socio-ecological character. Agriculture, in addition to production, performs a number of important functions: socio-demographic, cultural, ecological, recreational and spatial-communication. Therefore, when deciding to expand or reduce agrochemical production, it is necessary to take into account the damage caused, especially in the ecological and social spheres.

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These goals are mostly in nature. In accordance with these target devices, agriculture is based on the environmental technology of the area, its permissible technological loads, soil fertility and the standard of living of the population.

The third-level goal of economic development in the hierarchy of goals (other indicators of economic performance). They play a major role in developing development strategies, political and socio-economic goals in the form of restrictions. Thus, it is necessary to increase the economic efficiency of industries and enterprises in the implementation of restrictions of a political and socio-ecological nature in each place. The first group of goals dominates the federal level, the second is the provincial level, and the third is the level of individual enterprises.

It was considered that the food supply system consists of three subsystems: food consumption and nutrition of the population, actual production of food products, formation and distribution of food resources.

The goals and objectives of the bulk system of consumption of heat, approved by the government of the country in August 1998, can be justified on the basis of the concept of public policy in the healthy nutrition of the population, as approved in August 1998:

- human health is the most important priority of the state;
- food products should not harm human health;
- nutrition should not only meet the physiological needs of a person in food, but also perform preventive and therapeutic tasks;
- reasonable nutrition of children should receive special attention of the state;
- Nutrition should contribute to the protection of the human body from unknown environmental conditions;
- Healthy nutrition requirements are unified for all food products.

The criterion for assessing the nutritional level of the population is the level of meeting structural needs and the energy content of the food diet. The minimum nutritional level of the population in the amount and assortment of food, the minimum acceptable level in terms of the amount of nutrients and energy supply leads to the consumption of the consumer.

The main factors that reflect food safety are the absence of substances harmful to health in food or their concentration should not exceed the recommended level.

The subsystem of food production is mainly agro-industrial production. The level and pace of agro-horizontal production industries, their potential for expansion determine the country's food resources and food security.

The main field of agriculture is agriculture. First, the country's food production capabilities depend on the natural and economic conditions of its activity. A prerequisite for food security is food independence, which includes meeting food needs through local production. The idea is that the growth of the production of local Agro-Sanif Complex stimulates the development of many sectors of the economy.

To increase the interests of increasing the level of food supply for the population and the development of the agrochemical complex, it offers to use the opportunities of the International Labor Department and the world market. Based on the circumstances that alleviate the situation in the import food market, it helps to replace the shortage of local food, improve the range and quality of the population, and also plays a certain positive role in the formation of a competitive environment in the domestic market. However, it is not allowed to subsidize the subsidized goods of the exporters of domestic producers in the domestic market. Based on the interests of ensuring

food security, it is necessary to increase the dependence of agriculture, food and processing industry on the import of material and technical resources, as well as agriculture, food and processing industry.

One of the important conditions for the country's food independence is the effective operation of domestic tractors and agricultural machinery, mineral fertilizers, plant protection products, veterinary drugs, and technical means of the processing industry.

However, self-sufficiency for food, calculated as the ratio of domestic production to domestic consumption, does not indicate a country's level of food security and is therefore a generalization indicator. It should be noted that in some countries, the export of food and agricultural raw materials leads to poverty, and in other countries, on the contrary, the import of food contributes. At the same time, both groups are not dependent on food, because in the first case, the basis of food imports, as well as the export of economically highly developed countries, allows to guarantee the payment of food and raw materials necessary for them.

The subsystem of formation and distribution of food resources describes the level of physical and economic supply of food to different categories of the population, the state of the food market, the state of the food market, the size of the state food reserves.

The physical freedom of food means that it is not included in the corresponding payment capacity and is distinguished by its quantity and the population required in the retail network and food markets. As the volume and structure of food supply and the structure of rules adopted for them.

Economic use is the possibility of purchasing by purchasing different segments of the population, as well as by means of payment for the supply of food products by the state. In the country, as in a number of other countries, the economic availability of food is determined not only by the availability of market supply and the ability to produce it in private plots and in the garden (for own consumption in the summer. Sottakas)

Indicators describing the economic availability of food are indicators of the size and composition of food products purchased by different groups of the population in relation to the norm.

Food security refers to the state and society's compliance with food and food security due to natural disasters and other emergencies. For this, it is necessary to create continuously renewable strategic and operational food products and their distribution systems. The size of the operational federal and regional food reserves is determined by the supply and delivery in the food market, market conditions.

Adequacy of the state's strategic food reserves is the ability to provide the population with food in the amount of the minimum consumption basket in emergency situations.

When it fails to import food, world and domestic experience shows that a country that cannot pay for food imports becomes food dependent. At the same time, countries with self-sufficiency, calculated as the ratio of national product to the amount of domestic food production, may have high levels of consumer demand due to their lack of products. Food procurement significantly increases domestic food production. Each country determines its dependence on imported food based on its economic potential, international positions, foreign and exchange resources, the level of development of agro-industrial production, satisfaction for satisfaction, and other factors of internal and external order. For example, in Japan, the nutrition of food corresponds to the level of

food consumption of the population.

In addition, food products and food consumption are relatively poorly developed countries, as well as countries related to food consumption, and because hunger is not widespread, food products should be kept in mind when writing. . In the second case, Country i, food security, their food security depends on the import of food and raw materials for the production of their own products. In the loss of these external food products and food insecurity, their growth trends become a reality.

The country's high and unjustified dependence on some food products significantly reduces its economic security, because the purchase of food and raw materials for their production puts pressure on foreign exchange resources in addition to foreign exchange resources Debt . Increasing food production leads to the fact that the country is forced to pay with natural resources that it does not have and its role in the global economy is weakened. Import of food as a result of the sale of natural resources, natural resources, non-local, but foreign producers to some extent.

Taking into account the size and diversity of the country's regions, the issue of food support for regions is of particular importance, their objectively developed division is related to their export, self-sufficiency and import. liq. The first is characterized by natural conditions and agricultural land favorable for per capita food production, while the second has the least favorable conditions for agriculture.

In solving the problem of self-management of territories, its priority types are distinguished by food. The criteria for inclusion in the number of certain products are as follows: their satisfaction with the necessary components of the food diet in meeting the needs of the population; Transport, which ensures redistribution of commodity resources among commodity resources; stability of consumption and price stability in the food market and long-term shelf-life to create securities for price stability. Taking into account the priority of priority in ensuring food safety, it concerns grain, sugar, vegetable oil, milk and meat products, fish. Meeting the need for this type of products should be the subject of special care of the state legislative and executive authorities. The priority of grain production is explained by the country's consumption structure, where bread and bakery products occupy a very large specific gravity in the population's diet. The strategic value of grain in food nutrition is determined by the technological features of this product, which allow creating a reserve fund, especially in the event of crop and crop failure. Their importance is to guarantee market prices in the domestic market, for food purposes in the country and abroad, and emergency situations, emergency situations, food purposes, as well as livestock needs.

The high amount of food products of our country determines the priority of the grain industry in the state measures to support local agricultural products.

The country is one of the countries that has increased the consumption of sugar, which constitutes an important part of the necessary energy content of the food diet. Due to its preservation potential, sugar is an indispensable raw material component in the processing of fruit and berry products. With its high transportability and long-term shelf life, this product is widely redistributed and distributed between regions and is important in the formulation of food products.

The priority of the country's food is vegetable oil, two-thirds of which is used for food purposes. In the diet of the population, this product has a relatively small share compared to developed foreign countries, and its consumption is 2.5-3 times lower. However, animal fat, the resources of production, increase the need for mayonnaise, sauces, and the need for vegetable oil in the future is less taken into account. In addition, vegetable oil has a high transport capacity, for

which its non-losing funds can be redistributed between regions.

In the food supply, milk, milk products, and especially the country, which occupies one of the first places in the country, milk, dairy products, especially animal fat, because it occupies an important place, which occupies one of the first places in the world, occupies an important place. Dairy products, primarily cheese, milk powder and canned milk, are very portable and suitable for storage.

The importance of meat and its processing products in the food supply is determined by the increased consumption in the last three decades. Meat products with high energy and protein content are of great importance, especially in Northern regions and industrial occupations. In addition to cooked meat and chilled meat, meat products are also suitable in frozen form, especially for long-distance transportation and stockpiling.

A number of other very important products - potatoes, vegetables, fruits, berries, eggs are mostly self-sufficient. However, as they take initiative and respond to longevity, their value in resource reallocation and food creation increases.

Solving the problem of food support requires a combination of national and federal entities. All regions, first of all, to deal with poorly restored food products, self-intermediate product types, potatoes, vegetables, fruits, berries, eggs.

The problem is that there is sustainable food production in cities with a population of more than a million people, where 18 percent of the country's population lives today. Currently, the markets of these cities are mainly filled with imported food products and products produced by local food enterprises, including imported raw materials. It is necessary to restore limited agricultural products and restore long-term contractual relations for the city to order and use the financial resources that provide it, to supply the city with agricultural products and cheap products from other regions. The development of the market infrastructure allows to attract a large volume of products above the city order when it exceeds the city order.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it should be said that a special problem is the development of food products in the northern regions, the minimal opportunities for the development of agricultural production, limited to dispersion, fishing, fisheries, greenhouse plants and animal husbandry in imported feed. Away from the highly efficient commodity production zones, their food supply (including imports) is increasingly used for food and raw materials production (including imports) and for further development of secondary stocks. in order to develop more. For the northern regions, traditional food sources that supply agricultural products, seeds, fodder, young animals, so used "backyard" agricultural enterprises.

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